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Evidence of accomplishment

Report

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Shelf (NBZ), East Brazil Shelf (EBZ), South Brazil Shelf (SBZ), Patagonian Shelf (PAT), Benguela Current (BEN), Guinea Current (GUI), Canary Current (CAN), Iberian Coastal (IB), Celtic-Biscay Shelf (CELT), North Sea (NS), Norwegian Sea (NoS).

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1 Summary

This document was created as part of the H2020 All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture (ASTRAL) project, in support of Work Package 5 Climate – Ocean – Food. The ASTRAL project facilitated the development of new and improved innovative technology to support integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) production monitoring and management. It also investigated past and future environmental and climatic risks to aquaculture in the northern and southern Atlantic regions. This report draws from the findings of several public project reports to provide recommendations on best design, list of relevant parameters and most appropriate sensors and observing platforms for IMTA-system-specific monitoring programmes for climate change, Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs), pathogens, and microplastics. It should be noted that there is a distinction to be made between the monitoring of the production environment, and the monitoring of the ambient or incoming water environment; this document focusses on the latter.

The report is structured as follows: Chapter 2 introduces the concept of IMTA featuring the different IMTA systems types that were employed in the ASTRAL project; Chapter 3 discusses the climate related risk to IMTA and aquaculture; Chapter 4 focusses on the HAB related risks to IMTA and aquaculture; while Chapter 5 discusses pathogen related risks to IMTA and aquaculture; Chapter 6 considers microplastic in aquaculture; and lastly Chapter 7 discusses technology recommendations. Each of the sections are broken down, where applicable, into regional-related, system-related, and monitoring-related considerations; each section concludes with the specific monitoring recommendations related to the chapter topic. Summary tables of the system-specific monitoring recommendations for climate change, HABs and pathogens are provided in Chapter 8.

2 Introduction

Aquaculture is one of the fastest growing industries in the world and is increasingly recognised for its critical role in sustainable food production for the global population. However, the industry can be vulnerable to environmental risks - such as climate change, harmful algal blooms (HABs) and pathogens - and has the potential to negatively impact the surrounding environment, including contributing to the emission of microplastics into the marine environment.

Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) is an innovative practice that increases the sustainability of intensive aquaculture systems through an ecosystem-based approach. It combines the cultivation of species at two or more different trophic levels while taking advantage of their synergistic interactions and the ecosystem services that they provide. An IMTA system may include fed species (e.g. finfish), particulate organic nutrient extractive species (e.g. shellfish and other invertebrates, herbivorous fish) and dissolved inorganic nutrient extractive species (e.g. macro- and micro-algae and plants). An example of an IMTA system is provided in Figure 1. The implementation of IMTA practices assists in increasing the environmental sustainability, economic diversification, and social acceptability of the system.

Figure 1. Schematic of a potential open-water IMTA scenario. ©Marine Institute

Each IMTA system is unique in terms of siting, structure (**flow-through, land-based, open-water**), species cultivated, nutrient inputs and uptakes. These systems will each have a different risk profile and different vulnerabilities to variable short- and long-term environmental conditions, as well as to the introduction of biological hazards.

2.1 Overview of the ASTRAL IMTA labs

IMTA labs do not refer to a laboratory setup, but rather to the locations of the IMTA production sites of the ASTRAL project. The project gathers four established and one prospective (Argentina) IMTA labs using three different types of systems, namely Recirculating Aquaculture System (RAS) using Biofloc (Brazil), land-based pump ashore partially (50%) recirculated (South Africa), and open-water (Ireland, Scotland). For detailed information about the IMTA production, species trialled in the project and their production, welfare and health, please refer to ASTRAL project Deliverable 2.8¹.

Open-water IMTA

Open-water systems refer to species production that takes place at sea, where moorings are used to anchor the growing structures to the seabed. This type of system is continuously exposed to the ambient environment. An example of an open-water IMTA system is provided in Figure 1.

The **IMTA lab Ireland**, managed by the Marine Institute, is an open-water coastal marine system located off the west coast of Ireland, farming a combination of trophic species in differing structures on one production site (Figure 1). The location of the site in the Connemara area of Ireland is relatively sheltered, with no significant fetch or swell, and waves are produced by local wind conditions. It is subjected to runoff from rainfall, reducing salinity and increasing turbidity with high particulate loading. Due to runoff, salinity ranges from 24 to 35 ppt, but is typically greater than 32 ppt. Tidal range is approximately 5 m and water temperature ranges from 5 to 18 °C. Key to the cultivation of species in an IMTA scenario is the species interactions or established trophic linkage. The cultivation included fed species Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) and lumpfish (*Cyclopterus lumpus*); extractive species including Native oyster (*Ostrea edulis*) and seaweeds (*Saccharina latissima*, *Alaria esculenta*); and novel species including Spiny sea urchins (*Paracentrotus lividus*), among others (Figure 2).

¹ D2.8 Manuals for marine IMTA production, health, biosecurity and welfare.

Figure 2. The location and layout of the Ireland IMTA lab.

The **Scotland IMTA Lab**, managed by the Scottish Association for Marine Science (SAMS) in Oban, operates an experimental low-trophic aquaculture farm in Port-a-Bhuiltin on the Scottish west coast (Figure 3). The site consists of a one-hectare submerged tension grid situated approximately 250 m away from the mainland coast, with a tidal range up to 4.3 m and moderate average surface current speeds of 10 cm s^{-1} , which can vary between 0.1 to 550 cm s^{-1} throughout the year. Annual variation in sea surface temperature ranges from 6 to 15°C and salinity from 24 to 34 ppt (although typically above 32 ppt). As a research site, cultivated species and production scales vary from year to year depending on various research project interests and requirements, but has focused mainly on the cultivation of brown seaweeds (*Alaria esculenta*, *Saccharina latissima*) and native oysters (*Ostrea edulis*). Under ASTRAL, additional low trophic species were trialled, including brown (*Laminaria digitata*), red (*Palmaria palmata*) and green (*Ulva spp.*) seaweeds as well as king scallops (*Pecten maximus*) and sea urchins (*Echinus esculentus*).

Figure 3. SAMS IMTA lab Port-a-Bhuiltin location and site set-up for co-cultivation of various seaweed and shellfish species. A) Geographic location of the Scotland IMTA lab. B) General scheme of 1ha site, divided in 4 quadrants with one of them used to develop oyster growth. Data buoy and PAR chain are used to monitor several physical parameters at two water depths (1.5 and 3 metres) C) Zoom into the parcel with Oyster baskets, showing how these are placed within the system. Orange and black dots represent buoys to hold the system at right depth, brown lines the seaweeds.

The **prospective IMTA Lab Argentina**, designed by CONICET (*Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas*), assessed the feasibility of establishing IMTA in the Beagle Channel (Figure 4). It included evaluations of the suitability of employing local species to facilitate IMTA, long-term environmental and water quality assessments, and market studies. Port Almanza, a small artisanal fishing village located 70 km from Ushuaia, was identified as the ideal location since it had one of the highest ratings for the quality of the environment for mussel production, as granted by the National Service of Food Health and Quality (SENASA). The organisms selected for inclusion in potential IMTA production were: Blue mussel (*Mytilus chilensis*), Red sea urchin (*Loxechinus albus*), Small puyen or whitebait (*Galaxias maculatus*), and the halophyte Salicornia or samphire (*Salicornia magellanica*).

Figure 4. Proposed location of the future IMTA lab in the Beagle channel, Argentina.

Land-based IMTA

Within the context of the ASTRAL project, land-based IMTA refers to either RAS inshore biofloc systems or land-based pump ashore systems with partial water recirculation. These types of systems allow a certain level of control over some of the physical and chemical parameters within a production system, and provides some protection from the ambient environment – depending on the extent of the recirculation used and the location of the system.

The **South African IMTA Lab** consists of a partnership between the University of Cape Town (UCT), the Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE), and Viking Aquaculture². The IMTA lab is based at Buffeljags abalone farm, operated by Viking Aquaculture, which is a partially recirculating land-based commercial aquafarm located ca. 200 km east of Cape Town on a pristine stretch of coastline on the Cape south coast. The farm is modern, efficient and environmentally sustainable and is one of the first large commercial abalone farms in South Africa to consistently recirculate ca. 50% of their seawater by making use of the bio-remediation capacity of the green seaweed *Ulva lacunculata*. The farm currently has seven modular abalone-*Ulva* IMTA systems, called platforms, which are each composed of four clusters that each consist of one *Ulva* paddle-raceway and 42 abalone tanks (6 rows each made of 7 abalone raceway tanks) (Figure 5). The fresh seawater is pumped directly from the adjacent coastline into a settlement pond prior to entering the abalone clusters, consisting of sturdy fibreglass tanks where abalone are grown in suspended baskets. Seawater is circulated through the ponds, ensuring a constant supply of cool, aerated water for growing abalone. The species at the South African IMTA lab include fed species, i.e. the South African abalone (*Haliotis midae*) and the warm

² <https://www.vikingaquaculture.co.za/abalone/>

water sea urchin (*Tripneustes gratilla*); extractive species, including the seaweed *Ulva lacinulata*; and novel species, including the temperate sea urchin (*Parechinus angulosus*).

Figure 5. (A) Land-based pump-ashore IMTA system to produce abalone (*Haliotis midae*) and seaweed (*Ulva lacinulata*) at Buffeljags abalone. The photograph shows the modular abalone-*Ulva* systems, arranged as seven platforms on the farm, with each platform composed of four clusters each consisting of one *Ulva* paddle-raceway and several abalone tanks. (B) Schematic of *Ulva* raceway receiving effluent water from the abalone tanks (AEW_In) and bioremediated water (AEW_Out) leaving these tanks. (C) Schematic of the IMTA process at Buffeljags Abalone, where the effluent water leaving the abalone tanks is bioremediated by the *Ulva* before being mixed with 50% fresh seawater and returned to the abalone raceways.

The **Brazilian IMTA lab** is operated by the Federal University of Rio Grande (FURG) at the Marine Aquaculture Center in the Rio Grande do Sul located 300 m away from the shoreline in southern Brazil. The IMTA production system consists of a land-based closed Recirculating Aquaculture System (RAS) that stimulates the production of microbial aggregates (Biofloc system or BFT); this technology allows

super-intensive production (high density) in small spaces with minimal to no water renewal. BFT utilizes the action of microorganisms aggregated in flocs that perform multiple functions in the system, including the control of nitrogen compounds, being a feed source for shrimp, tilapia and oysters, and facilitating the reduction of some infections and diseases. Species cultivated at the site include white shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*), sea lettuce (*Ulva fasciata*) and sea asparagus (*Salicornia neei*), native oysters (*Crassostrea gasar*), and tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*).

Figure 6. The location of the Marine Aquaculture Center of the Federal University of Rio Grande (FURG) in southern Brazil [top]; and a schematic design of IMTA Biofloc Technology in land-based pump-inshore IMTA system for the production of shrimp (Compartment 1), tilapia and oyster (Compartment 2) and seaweed-*Ulva* (Compartment 3) [bottom].

The IMTA lab has nine experimental shrimp ponds (600 m² each), three greenhouses for research with shrimp production in bioflocs, one pilot commercial size greenhouse for shrimp production (two tanks of 280 m² each) and one multi-trophic greenhouse (Figure 6; six systems with three tanks each), in addition to a laboratory with a shrimp maturation sector, shrimp hatchery sector with commercial size

tanks, sectors of live food production (Artemia and phytoplankton) and water quality laboratory. Each of the six independent IMTA systems (Figure 6) consists of three components: a 20 m³ raceway containing the biofloc community and shrimp; a 3 m³ raceway stocked with fish and oysters suspended in mesh bags; and a 3 m³ circular tank housing the macro algae.

2.2 Stakeholder engagement and perceptions

An online ASTRAL workshop was organised during June 2023 with the aim of gathering feedback from aquaculture stakeholders about their knowledge and perceptions regarding the topics of climate change, HABs, pathogens and microplastic emissions in the context of aquaculture. The workshop flyer and agenda (Appendix A) were disseminated to key stakeholders via email, through the Aquaculture Helix, and were advertised on ASTRAL social media platforms for several weeks. The workshop included presentations about the ASTRAL project, and research summaries relating to Atlantic aquaculture under the four themes of climate change, HABs, pathogens, and microplastics emissions. After the presentations, questions were put to the participants to allow the workshop organisers to gather knowledge from the stakeholders using the electronic platform - Mentimeter.com (Menti). The aim was to encourage active engagement with attendees, to gather input and opinion on the workshop topics. Using Menti polls the audience were shown the results of these polls in real time. These same questions were also put in an online survey, which was circulated to persons who registered for the workshop but could not attend, as well as via social media (any duplication of inputs was removed). 117 people registered to attend the webinar, and 50 unique viewers attended (all or part of) the workshop, while 8 participants completed the survey after the workshop; most of the participants were researchers (Figure 7), with only three aquaculturalists, one regulator, but no policy makers.

Figure 7. Location of the 50 workshop attendees (obtained from registration form) and 8 online survey participants [left], and a description of the participants (38 responses) [right].

The workshop participants were assessed on their perceptions of the level of threat/risk to aquaculture associated with each of the four workshop themes (Figure 8). The threat from HABs were rated highest, at a level of intermediate to high risk, followed by the threat of Climate Change. The risks from pathogens and microplastics were perceived as intermediate.

Figure 8. The level of threat/risk to aquaculture associated with the different variables (34 responses). [0 = very low risk; 10 = very high risk]

While there was a good awareness about existing regional monitoring programs for HABs, pathogens and Climate Change variables, there appeared to be much more uncertainty around (or potentially lack of) monitoring programmes for microplastics emissions (Figure 9); similarly, participants were also generally aware of national policies regarding monitoring for HABs and pathogens, however there was less knowledge and more uncertainty regarding policies for monitoring the variables related to climate change, and even less awareness of those relating to monitoring the emissions of microplastics.

The stakeholder perspectives provide valuable insights into potential knowledge-gaps and barriers regarding regional monitoring programmes, available technologies to perform these actions, and where future efforts could be placed in terms of science communication and/or regulatory and policy development. The remainder of this document endeavours to address some of these points.

Figure 9. Question: There are [top] monitoring programs in my region and/or [bottom] national policies in my region that require aquaculture operations to monitor for each of the following variables (33 responses). [1 = strongly disagree; 5 = strongly agree]

3 Climate related risks to IMTA and aquaculture

Different farmed organisms can tolerate different ranges in the chemical and physical properties of the water in an aquaculture facility (Figure 10). Maintaining water quality parameters within the optimal ranges for each organism helps to ensure their health and performance, while outside of these ranges the organisms may become stressed, resulting in poor growth, behavioural changes, diseases and mortalities. Climate change can affect both the variability and trends in several of the physico-chemical parameters relevant to marine aquaculture.

Figure 10. Optimal (in green) and tolerance ranges (blue arrow ends) of some of the water quality parameters for key ASTRAL cultivated species. ***Salmo salar* dissolved oxygen tolerance range is 70-100% relative to temperature and pH

To identify climate related risks to IMTA and aquaculture, climate change induced trends were calculated along the Atlantic coast for the last 3-5 decades; a comprehensive overview of this study is provided in ASTRAL Deliverable 5.1³. The identification of trends was based on quality controlled observational data for sea surface temperature (SST), sea surface salinity (SSS), surface dissolved oxygen, pCO₂ and surface nitrate, as well as observation-based calculations of pH. These results were used to identify environmental risk, seen as an acceleration of trends in the last decades. Regional consideration and monitoring considerations and recommendations were based on these results. It is

³ D5.1 Climate Vulnerability along the Atlantic Coast. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10848745>

noted that the results give an initial indication of the expected environmental changes, but do not evaluate the vulnerability of an IMTA farm's production to these environmental changes. To create more sustainable IMTA value-chains, the results must be considered in combination with the sensitivity of the IMTA species to these environmental changes.

3.1 Regional considerations

Regional long-term observations of the variables in question are required in order to distinguish climate trends unambiguously from natural variability. Long-term, frequent observational data is readily available for land surface temperature. The determination of a long-term trend is much more challenging for oceanic variables as *in situ* observations of the ocean are sparse in both space and time. For this reason, the available data were collated into regions (here: Large Marine Ecosystems, see Figure 11) in order to identify long-term trends.

Despite collation, data for the South Brazil Shelf Large Marine Ecosystem was still sparse and had the least coverage of all ecosystems adjacent to ASTRAL's prospective IMTA site. Nevertheless, the South Brazil Shelf and the Large Marine Ecosystems surrounding the other ASTRAL IMTA sites (Patagonian Shelf, Benguela Current and Celtic-Biscay Shelf) comprise enough *in situ* data to allow for confident climate trend estimates of SST and SSS. In all four regions, *in situ* nitrate and oxygen measurements were too sparse to allow for a confident trend estimate, although the oxygen trends were in line with previously published estimates. The coverage of *in situ* pCO₂ data and the confidence in calculated trends in pH and pCO₂ were strongly dependent on the region and the time period considered.

Of the four considered Large Marine Ecosystems, that surrounding ASTRAL's IMTA sites in **Ireland and Scotland** (the Celtic-Biscay Shelf) is the most vulnerable to climate change in terms of the selected variables, as it experiences a clear long-term warming (1957-2020) and an alarming warming acceleration during 1980-2020. The long-term warming signal is accompanied by a moderate decline in surface oxygen during the period 1957-2020 (confirmed by Ito et al., 2017⁴) as well as a strong increase in pCO₂ and a corresponding strong decline in surface pH during the period 1980-2021.

The Large Marine Ecosystem adjacent to ASTRAL's IMTA site in **South Africa** has experienced a moderate long-term warming (1957-2020), and a deceleration in warming for the period 1980-2020.

⁴ Ito, Minobe, Long, and Deutsch, 2017: Upper ocean O₂ trends: 1958–2015, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 44, pp. 4214– 4223, doi:10.1002/2017GL073613.

A decreasing trend in O₂ was also identified during the period 1957-2020, with a decline in pH between 1980 and 2021.

Figure 11. Location of the 17 considered Large Marine Ecosystems of the Atlantic ocean: Newfoundland-Labrador Shelf (NFL), Scotian Shelf (SCO), Northeast U.S. Continental Shelf (NUSC), Southeast U.S. Continental Shelf (S USC), Gulf of Mexico (GMEX), Caribbean Sea (CARI), North Brazil Shelf (NBZ), East Brazil Shelf (EBZ), South Brazil Shelf (SBZ), Patagonian Shelf (PAT), Benguela Current (BEN), Guinea Current (GUI), Canary Current (CAN), Iberian Coastal (IB), Celtic-Biscay Shelf (CELT), North Sea (NS), Norwegian Sea (NoS).

The Large Marine Ecosystem adjacent to ASTRAL's IMTA site in **Brazil** experienced a sustained moderate warming for both periods (1957-2020 and 1980-2020) and a strong increase in pCO₂ and decline in pH between 1980 to 2021. Yet, it also shows potentially positive trends for the IMTA-system with an increasing trend of O₂ for the period 1957-2020, confirmed by Ito and co-authors (2017).

The Patagonian Shelf Large Marine Ecosystem (adjacent to the **Beagle channel** and the prospective IMTA site in Argentina) displayed a very slow warming over the long-term period 1957-2020, with some cooling over the more recent period (1980-2020). It also experienced a significant decrease in SSS for 1957-2020 and this trend is accelerating with time. Consistent with the slow surface warming and a surface freshening, the trend-estimates identify a less intense pCO₂ increase and pH decline for the period 1980-2021, with a negligible trend in O₂ for the period 1957-2020. Due to data sparsity, the results for O₂ should be considered with care, but they are in line with results from Ito and co-authors (2017). Hence, the prospective IMTA lab in Argentina might be less vulnerable to climate change.

However, this suggestion should be tested when longer time-series with new ASTRAL measurements are available.

3.2 System type considerations

These results have the most significant implications for open-water systems as they are most exposed to changes in the ambient environment. Open ocean-based aquafarms are directly impacted by the physical conditions of the ocean water column, with no realistic human intervention options aside from perhaps changing the depth of cages, or the selection of seasonal farming only. In these cases, siting the location of the farm in physical environmental conditions conducive to the cultured species, is of vital importance. The climate trend for the IMTA sites in Ireland and Scotland indicates the need to cultivate species that tolerate a wide range of variability in temperature and oxygen, or species that benefit from the occurring changes.

Land-based systems have more control over the production conditions, such that the species produced are not required to tolerate the changing environmental conditions in the adjacent open-ocean directly. However, in many cases land-based ponds or tanks are exposed to the elements, and are directly affected by seasonal and daily weather changes, including day-night warming and cooling. These changing conditions might lead to increased costs implicit in controlling production conditions for land-based pump-ashore systems, dependent on the energy needed to transform the water quality of the pumped water.

3.3 Monitoring considerations

Aquaculture stakeholders identified the lack of policy around climate change variables, the high cost of monitoring, and the lack of regional long-term time-series data as barriers to monitoring for climate change (Figure 12). The ASTRAL project is directly addressing some of these issues through the development of cost-effective technologies in support of IMTA with the ASTRAL Technology Asset 3 (TA3), a Low-Cost Internet of Things (IoT) kit at the forefront of real-time physico-chemical parameter monitoring. It comprises a datalogger with support for various IoT communication protocols and provides a cost-effective solution for monitoring in real-time water parameters such as temperature, dissolved oxygen, salinity, and turbidity. It is self-powered, allowing it to operate efficiently in diverse environmental conditions, and has been deployed at multiple IMTA labs in site-specific configurations (Figure 13). The IoT kit's operations are integrated into the Artificial Intelligence (AI) Data Analytics Platform (TA7 - AIDAP) for real-time aquatic data acquisition and analysis. The Low Cost IoT kits

comprise a modular solution capable of dealing with different IMTA needs and constrains. The AIDAP platform integrates various ASTRAL technologies to support resilient aquaculture in the face of climate change. It enables the analysis and storage of long-term time series data for monitoring nutrients, harmful algal blooms (HABs), microplastics, physico-chemical conditions and other important variables.

Figure 12. Question: What are the barriers to monitoring for climate change? (31 responses)

It should be noted that a distinction can be made between environmental or ambient/incoming water quality monitoring requirements, as opposed to those of operational system water quality monitoring (i.e. in terms of husbandry), which may require more frequent measurements. However, it is important to have knowledge of the potential ranges of variability that are associate with tidal, diurnal, event-scale, and seasonal changes in the ambient environment to gain an understanding of the background state – this is also useful for choosing the appropriate location and time of day for taking long term environmental measurements.

IMTA and aquaculture operations should be encouraged to maintain well quality-controlled environmental measurements in long term monitoring databases, as data spanning significant time periods could reveal important business insight, e.g. via determining the difference between interannual and decadal variations and climate trends. Sharing of these data in national or international data repositories should also be encouraged (e.g., PANGAEA⁵, SEANOE⁶, Environmental

⁵ www.pangaea.de

⁶ www.seanoe.org

Data Initiative repository⁷), following FAIR principles. Currently, the work of climate scientists in confidently identifying long-term climate trends and trends in marine heat waves is hindered by the scarcity of *in situ* quality-controlled ocean data. Only a substantial increase in such data would enable the identification of regional drivers of faster or slower climate trends with confidence. This would facilitate future projection of these trends; ultimately benefiting the sustainability of aquaculture businesses.

Figure 13. Low cost IoT kit deployed in different IMTA labs: South Africa (left), Brazil (lower right) and Ireland (upper right).

3.4 Monitoring recommendations

Given the sparsity of existing *in situ* measurements of climate-related variables, and the variable nature of regional and site-specific climate-driven changes, the value of investing in well-characterised farming environments over long time periods is clear. Balanced with the cost of ongoing monitoring, the following set of recommendations has been developed to support the success of IMTA production over the timescales affected by annual and interannual changes:

- At all sites temperature should be monitored at the minimum on the surface, but additionally a sample at depth will be worthwhile in order to capture changes in stratification. It is recommended that these measurements be performed twice a day.

⁷ portal.edirepository.org/nis/home.jsp

- Where salinity appears to be vulnerable to change (e.g. at the prospective site in the Beagle Channel) increased attention to monitoring salinity is recommended to follow up on the indications of decreasing sea surface salinity in the surrounding Large Marine Ecosystem. Given the general lack of data for all climate related variables at this site, there is opportunity to develop a fit-for-purpose monitoring system here, covering all the essential variables.
- As a critical determinant of the wellbeing of cultivated aquatic species, dissolved oxygen should be monitored daily at all sites, preferably measured both at the IMTA site and upstream/downstream of the site to catch changes over a larger area.
- There are almost no data on inorganic nutrients at the IMTA sites or in the surrounding Large Marine Ecosystems. It is recommended that as a minimum, nitrate is regularly measured for monitoring and trend assessment, given its importance for kelp growth. These measurements could be done weekly to monthly.
- For the Southern Benguela Upwelling System, regionally optimized satellite data products have been shown to be very informative. Developing analogous data products specifically tailored to other IMTA regions would be very useful.

4 HAB related risks to IMTA and aquaculture

Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) are algae that cause disruption to ecosystem function or aquaculture operations in a variety of ways, including: the production of toxins or harmful metabolites that affect animal health; the bioaccumulation of toxins in animals – affecting their safety for human consumption; mechanical damage (e.g. clogging animal gills); or by causing low oxygen events following the collapse and decay of high biomass blooms. While several of these impacts are related to algal density, even low algal concentrations can be dangerous depending on the degree of toxicity of the algae. HABs can include various types and species: while usually associated with dinoflagellates in the marine environment, they can also involve diatoms, raphidophytes and cyanobacteria. A comprehensive overview of the biotic and abiotic conditions favouring HAB development can be found in ASTRAL Deliverable 5.2⁸

4.1 Regional considerations

While HABs are ubiquitous around the world, species vary regionally depending on their preference for different environmental conditions related to temperature, salinity, turbulence, light, and nutrient composition. Increases in nutrient loading, changes in agriculture and aquaculture practices, overfishing, ballast water discharge, and global climate change may all be important in the global increase in HABs (Glibert & Burkholder, 2006⁹). HAB formation mechanisms are complex and vary between species, time and season, and location. Risk factors driving favourable HAB conditions are therefore highly regional, and dependent also on the type of IMTA system. In general, algal species proliferate when environmental conditions (e.g., nutrient and light availability, temperature, and salinity) are optimal for cell growth. Other biological (e.g., vertical migration, grazing, viral infection, and parasitism) and physical (e.g., transport, currents, stratification) processes determine if enhanced cell growth will result in biomass accumulation. Further, cell physiology, genetic variation of toxin production, life cycles, and strain specificity adds to the challenge of understanding HABs dynamics. Harmful algal species are often found in stratified and nutrified waters. Many site-specific risk factors have been identified at each ASTRAL IMTA lab (Table 1) which contribute to creating this optimal environment for harmful algal blooms. These risk factors are directly or indirectly linked to an increase

⁸ D5.2 Biotic and Abiotic Conditions Favouring HAB Development and Associated Future Risks. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10848799>

⁹ Glibert, P. M., & Burkholder, J. M. (2006). The Complex Relationships Between Increases in Fertilization of the Earth, Coastal Eutrophication and Proliferation of Harmful Algal Blooms. *Ecology of Harmful Algae*, 341–354.

in nutrients such as the cause for run-offs or an increase in stratifications due to changes in meteorological and oceanographic conditions.

Table 1. Risk factors associated with harmful bloom events per IMTA region.

Risk factor	Argentina (Open-water, prospective)	Brazil (Land-based)	Ireland (Open-water)	Scotland (Open-water)	South Africa (Land-based)
River run-off Potential for increased nutrients and organic matter	X	X	X		
Agricultural run-off Potential for increased nutrients			X		
Urban wastewater Potential for increased nutrients, other organic matter, and chemical pollutants		X	X		X
Glacier run-off Cause salinity and temperature changes resulting in water stratification and changes the chemical (mineral) composition of the water column	X				
Upwelling Potential for increased nutrients, salinity changes					X
Stratification Preferred condition for many HAB species; increased potential for nutrient limitation/stress	X			X	
Current changes Potential for advection of blooms toward aquaculture facility		X		X	
Salinity changes May result in stratification of the water column and may favour salinity tolerant species	X	X	X	X	
Severe rainfall May cause water stratification and salinity changes which favour more low salinity tolerant species such as cyanobacteria.		X	X		
Severe weather events Storms may increase river run-off, leading to salinity changes and causing high nutrient load and organic matter and increase nutrient and organic matter load		X	X	X	X
Nutrification Increased nutrients and changes of optimal nutrient ratios. Preferred condition for many HAB species.	X				X
Changes in light levels Increased light important for bloom development	X		X		
High shipping area Vector for dispersal of HABs and cysts (e.g. in ballast water)		X		X	
Pollution Chemicals can potentially change nutrient and trace metal (i.e. Iron) availability. Chemicals can affect (higher) trophic levels causing a community composition shift. Plastic pollution can be a vector for dispersal of HABs due to cyst attachment.		X			X

4.2 IMTA system type considerations

Open-ocean systems are completely exposed to the ambient environmental conditions. Site selection for production needs to be carefully considered to avoid regions prone to the development of HABs. Open systems production and risks vary by year due to the weather conditions and the patchiness of HAB occurrences; this results in HAB impact being more severe in some years compared to others.

Closed and partially closed systems have more control over the environmental conditions. For example, the partial recirculation system of the South Africa IMTA lab site offers the potential for full recirculation for short periods (12-48h), which could be used during times when HABs are present at the location of the intake pipe. Meanwhile in the Brazilian context, water pumped to the farm from the estuary could be treated to avoid any cyanobacteria entering the production system.

Several risk factors, such as agricultural run-off and glacial melt water, are very location specific and have a large impact on the IMTA especially in open systems and deep understanding for each site is required.

4.3 Monitoring considerations

No single factor is responsible for HABs, but rather a complex interaction of biological, physical, and chemical factors is synergistically required. Seasonal and interannual variability as well as the local environment needs to be assessed in order to make monitoring recommendations. Nutrient enrichment of coastal water has been indicated as the leading cause in the increase in HAB incidence. However, nutrient loading alone is not sufficient to explain the increase in the number of HABs occurrences and a specific set of circumstances need to come together to provide the optimal conditions for bloom formation such as stable water column, optimum temperature, salinity, and light conditions. Temperature has a strong influence on phytoplankton community composition, with increasing annual temperatures broadening the window of seasonal HAB occurrence. Therefore, monitoring across the water column is recommended for nutrients, salinity, temperature, currents and stratification, as a basis for the causal environmental factors of HAB occurrence and proliferation.

Figure 14. Question: What are the barriers to monitoring for HABs in your region? (27 responses).

Determination of the presence of certain HAB-prone species is a fundamental aspect of a monitoring programme. However, stakeholder engagement has indicated that a lack of personnel with the relevant experience (i.e. for HAB identification and enumeration) and the high cost of monitoring were the primary barriers in monitoring for HABs (Figure 14). The ASTRAL project addressed these aspects through the development of TA5, an AI vision sensor for phytoplankton monitoring. The ASTRAL device has embedded AI vision models running on the open-source PlanktoScope¹⁰ platform (Figure 15), capable of imaging particles >10µm, and provided a cost-effective alternative to commercial products. Initial ASTRAL efforts to develop a phytoplankton genera classification system using optical AI technology highlighted constraints in the availability of appropriate datasets for AI training as well as taxonomy issues relating to the initial list of target phytoplankton for HAB monitoring. Following consultation with specialist taxonomists, a new list of target phytoplankton species for identification was developed according to the needs of IMTA labs using monocultures of bloom-forming species to address data gaps while supporting model fine-tuning and the validation of AI HAB identification. The result is a benchtop standalone device that supports automated image acquisition from water sample flow within a data acquisition chamber, allowing the user to narrow down genera-level classification for several harmful algae, demonstrating the significant potential of affordable technologies.

¹⁰ <https://www.planktoscope.org/>

Figure 15. ASTRAL Technology Asset 5 prototype based on the PlanktoScope platform.

4.4 Monitoring recommendations

While HAB monitoring should always be considered in the regionally appropriate context according to the specific geographic, seasonal and climatic risk factors, some general recommendations on monitoring HAB indicators and physico-chemical risk factors can be made for all sites:

- In many instances HABs are strongly associated with elevated biomass, and routine and frequent monitoring of Chlorophyll a (fluorescence) for non-species specific algal biomass estimates is fundamental. Monitoring could be done *in situ* (continuous), by field samples (daily) or using satellite data (daily).
- Species identification can be performed via microscopy or using a technological solution, e.g. FlowCam¹¹, PlanktoScope. Government guidelines for HAB monitoring in Scotland at shellfish cultivation sites are every fortnight to once a month during low season (October-March) and weekly during high season (April-September). In regions without specific national guidelines the monitoring could be done weekly over low risk periods, and adjusted to a higher frequency according to season/risk (i.e. daily during bloom season, with frequency increasing after harmful cell counts are detected).

¹¹ <https://www.fluidimaging.com/>

- Phytoplankton growth is very sensitive to nutrient ratios, and these should be monitored regularly with *in situ* field samples (monthly) of Nitrate, Phosphate, Ammonium, Silica, dissolved organic matter concentrations.
- Salinity should be measured either *in situ* or from field samples (weekly), and should be monitored across the depth range of the IMTA site to account for any stratification.
- Currents play a significant role in forecasting bloom movement and therefore risk of impact on IMTA sites: satellite data or models (daily), *in situ* (continuous) using a mooring.
- Upwelled nutrient rich water can prime a system for HAB growth. Temperature and upwelling should be monitored regularly using either satellite data or models (daily), field sampling (daily), and/or *in situ* (continuous) methods.
- Stratification, especially following an upwelling event, is a physical driver of HAB risk. To detect stratification *in situ* water temperature and salinity monitoring should be done both at the surface and at an appropriate depth (daily/continuous) covering at a minimum the depth range of the IMTA production site.

5 Pathogen related risks to IMTA and aquaculture

All animal species are susceptible to disease, and these risks are elevated in constrained farming conditions and in the context of climate change. In aquaculture, the presence and proliferation of disease-causing pathogens is a primary consideration in the management of animal health and the mitigation of commercial losses. Pathogens are diverse regionally and the risk of proliferation and impact varies according to cultivated species as well as the environment. Pathogens are not generally well monitored until the appearance of diseased stock. The primary aim of a low-cost monitoring programme is to employ emerging technologies to identify the absence or presence of known pathogens in accordance with the identified site- and species- driven risk factors. Monitoring should be directed towards predicting and preventing disease outbreaks, and as such an understanding of pathogen-favourable environments is essential. An integrated monitoring system of environmental variables, animal response (via biosensors) in conjunction with pathogen identification (via molecular tools) supports a holistic understanding of risk and allows for targeted interventions as risk is elevated.

A comprehensive overview of the main microbial pathogens that are capable of severely affecting productivity in each of the ASTRAL IMTA labs, descriptions of the current detection methods in aquaculture facilities, and emerging technologies to improve early warning systems, is provided in ASTRAL deliverable 5.3¹².

5.1 Regional considerations

The ASTRAL project includes four active IMTA labs: two in Europe (Ireland and Scotland), one in Africa (South Africa) and one in South America (Brazil). Moreover, one prospective IMTA lab location is evaluated in Argentina. The IMTA labs include open coastal (Ireland, Scotland), partially recirculating land-based (South Africa) and 100% recirculating land-based (Brazil) systems focusing on production of fish, mollusc, echinoderm, crustacean and macroalgae species. The description and directives applicable to each ASTRAL IMTA lab are described below

Europe

In terms of regulations, there are several European directives and regulations governing the production of aquatic organisms to ensure that health and welfare standards for organisms, produce

¹² D5.3 Monitoring of Microbial Diversity and Early Warning of Pathogens. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10849143>

and consumers are upheld. Animal health is legislated in order to control the presence and spread of disease. The European Council focuses on animal health for aquaculture animals and products thereof, and on the prevention and control of certain diseases in aquatic animals. The Directive also covers significant diseases which are widespread in certain parts of the European Community but are absent from other parts. These diseases can cause significant economic losses at a local level.

South Africa

The South African Department of Forestry, Fisheries, and the Environment (DFFE) has been entrusted to lead the development of sustainable aquaculture in South Africa and has been designated as the lead agency for the promotion, development and marketing of aquaculture and aquaculture products. In this regard, the DFFE has developed a National Aquatic Animal Health Strategic Framework (NASF) to provide overarching strategic guidance for the management, control and regulation of aquatic animal health, welfare and disease management in South Africa. Protocols and standards have been developed specifically for aquaculture, addressing issues such as disease-free zones and stock movement, emergency response and preparedness, quarantine, listing of diseases, prevention of suffering, disposal of mortalities, decontamination, biosecurity, operation of harvesting vessels and processing facilities, and compliance and enforcement. The specific conditions are outlined in the various types of permits required to engage in marine aquaculture.

Brazil

The Special Secretary for Aquaculture and Fisheries (*Secretaria Especial de Aqüicultura e Pesca – SEAP*) is the main authority for the management and development of fisheries and aquaculture in Brazil. SEAP Normative Instruction No.3 of 2004 regards aquaculture as the cultivation, breeding or holding in captivity, with commercial purposes, of organisms whose life cycle develops, in natural conditions, totally or partially in an aquatic environment. Within all the aquaculture sectors, the shrimp sector is the best organized industry of the aquaculture sector in Brazil. Thus, the Brazilian Shrimp Growers Association (*ABCC - Associação Brasileira de Criadores de Camarão*) has prepared four codes for good management practices, concerning shrimp farm management, shrimp feed production, shrimp hatchery, and processing plants

5.2 System type considerations

Open-water

The open coastal IMTA systems (Ireland and Scotland) are highly susceptible to several bacteria, viruses and parasites, most of them more prevalent in spring/summer when water temperatures increase. Moreover, disease outbreaks are harder to control in these systems due to their location.

Land-based

The partially recirculating land-based IMTA system (South Africa) has not experienced any major disease outbreaks, no WOAHP notifiable diseases have been identified from the system, and routine surveillance methodologies/ programs are currently implemented.

The Biofloc recirculating land-based IMTA system (Brazil) is similarly characterized by a low incidence of disease outbreaks, with the Biofloc identified as the key variable for reducing pathogen entry into the system. However, dysbiosis caused by several bacteria, such as *Streptococcus*, *Vibrio spp.* and *Cyanobacteria*, has been identified as a primary concern for the system and no standardized surveillance methods are currently in place.

5.3 Monitoring considerations

A large number of potential diseases and pathogens have been identified in the various IMTA systems, some of which have also been listed as notifiable by the World Organization for Animal Health (WOAH). All species within these aquaculture systems are susceptible to emerging diseases caused by various pathogenic bacteria, viruses, fungi and parasites. Outbreaks are expected to increase due to climate change, with open water systems being the most vulnerable ones. Understanding the nature of these pathogenic outbreak is crucial to keep the system healthy. Most problematic diseases are caused by bacteria, viruses and other pathogens. Control of these outbreaks include antibiotics, probiotics, vaccines and control of the stress factors. But early warning and identification are crucial for the detection and prevention of outbreaks. Most of these pathogens are currently monitored by good manipulation and control of general infestation intensity, acting once signs of disease have already been identified. For the detection and controlling of pathogens, it is important to identify the pathogen, its presence and absence, but it is also important to understand the environment in which they grow best, and how the host health is susceptible for infection.

Several factors can be identified to use as a sign to prevent outbreaks. Based on early known symptomatology of the disease, the best tools can be identified for detection, control and monitoring. Based on the microbiome potential to boost sustainable ways of cultivation and the exposed risk by pathogens diseases, there is a high necessity to improve technologies which could provide us as much as possible information about the health status of the system. This improvement has to consider the following parameters: sensitivity, specificity, speed, cost and feasibility to implement these technologies in the field. From now, an extensive review of the emerging technologies for surveillance and anticipate the pathogens outbreaks with species/region-specific methodologies has been done. Future methodologies for detection and monitoring of pathogens in IMTA labs should focus on a combination between molecular tools and biosensors. While molecular tools provide specificity and accuracy, they require pre-processing and careful handling of samples, as well as high cost and careful manufacturing of the equipment. Stakeholder engagement has indicated the high costs of the tests as the greatest constraint to monitoring for pathogens (Figure 16). Biosensors provide cheap, fast but they still need development for proper efficient implementation. As mentioned, it is key to improve monitoring and control of the environment by implementing new technologies that can provide information of IMTA lab (or others aquaculture systems) health status in real time, allowing for monitoring of possible pathogen presence. Although molecular tools provide specificity and accuracy when detecting pathogens, biosensors allow for fast, easy detection and monitoring of pathogens in IMTA lab systems. Thus, the surveillance strategies in the aquaculture industry should standardize the combination between molecular tools and biosensors, providing a more accurate, cost-effective, faster, and easier handling of data when it comes to pathogen detection and identification. The standardization of these methods and subsequent increase of the amount of data generated from the systems, could lead to the implementation of novel machine learning and specie/system-specific predicting models which are needed to anticipate pathogens outbreaks.

Figure 16. Question: What are the barriers to monitoring for pathogens in your region? (27 responses)

5.4 Monitoring recommendations

Depending on the IMTA system different types of biosensors or molecular tools are recommended, based on the needs and characteristics of the labs, feasibility, and pathogens present in the systems.

- The open-water coastal IMTA systems: Firstly, the introduction of biosensors in tagged fish (e.g. AEFishBIT operculum), should be evaluated to obtain real-time data about fish stress/health within the system. Early pathogen identification should then be based on samples obtained from mucosal tissues using field-compatible methods such as portable qPCR machines or Lateral Flow Biosensors (LFB). Based on previous studies, qPCR techniques seem to be optimal for bacterial pathogens (e.g., *A. Salmonicida*, *Tenacibaculum*, *Vibrio spp.*, *M. vicosa*), meanwhile LFB are more optimal for rapid detection of viruses (e.g., *Novirhabdoviruses*, *Oyster Herpes Virus*). As for sea lice (*C. elongates/L. Salmonis*), several traps based on Light-emitting diode biosensors have been used to reduce the sea lice infestation. Further technologies based on techniques described for other parasites (e.g., qPCR for their adult life stage) together with the improvement of eDNA methodologies and machine learning implementation should be considered to tackle this problematic pathogen before an outbreak occurs.
- Partially recirculating land-based IMTA system: New and more sophisticated technologies to improve early detection of specific pathogens are recommended, particularly for *Vibrio* species (e.g., *V. anguillarum*, *V. parahaemolyticus*, *V. harveyi* and *V. splendis*), *Haliotid herpesvirus-1* and several parasites (e.g., *Amoeba*, *Spionids* and *sabellids*). Moreover, considering the type of system, eDNA samples from the incoming or effluent seawater can be used to anticipate the entry or presence of specific pathogens in the system. Thus, for this type of sampling, digital qPCR is proposed for virulence related genes (e.g., hemolysin production, gyrase subunit B or malate dehydrogenase) of *Vibrio* species, lateral flow biosensors for *herpesvirus* and multi-locus barcoding for the identification of different parasite species. Moreover, wireless sensors networks are recommended for monitoring water quality parameters and microbiome metabarcoding is proposed to generate continuous data to anticipate system dysbiosis and a possible disease outbreak occurrence.
- The Biofloc recirculating land-based IMTA system: analysis of eDNA samples collected from the Biofloc are proposed to monitor the presence or change in abundance (increase) of potential pathogens described for the system. For this, the combination of Wireless biosensor, microbiome metabarcoding and digital qPCR are proposed for improving surveillance of this system.

- The prospective IMTA system in Argentina also present several potential pathogens that will need to be considered previously to implementation. Although the SENASA (Servicio Nacional de Sanidad y Calidad Agroalimentaria) is improving the notification and communication of disease events, further work should be done to identify the most problematic pathogens impacting the aquaculture industry in the Patagonian area and technologies to monitor the systems. Regarding the pathogens identified, digital qPCR and biosensors (LFB and wireless sensor) are suggested to be implemented in these new IMTA laboratories.

6. Microplastics

Plastic pollution has been increasing globally and has become an issue of growing concern, leading to many local, regional, and international initiatives aimed at better understanding of the sources, processes of degradation and distribution, and the impacts on the marine environment. Plastic equipment used in the fisheries and aquaculture industries contribute to emissions of microplastics into the sea, which likely have negative consequences for the marine environment and living organisms.

One of the specific objectives of the ASTRAL project is to map the distribution of pollutants of emerging concern in the selected IMTA open water labs, with a specific focus on aquaculture related microplastic pollution fingerprint assessment. The ASTRAL Deliverable 5.4¹³ describes the development of a robust and reliable sampling device, describes sample preparation and analysis methods, with recommendations for routine monitoring. The recommendations given in this section are general, and not regionally or IMTA system-specific. Rather, a monitoring plan aimed at understanding the short- and long-term fingerprint of plastic litter implicit in industrial production is recommended. Several types of monitoring approaches can be considered, as there are a number of different methodologies and technologies available. Overall, monitoring strategies can complement one another in the sense that the same observational methods and measurements can be used for different investigations. It is important to recognize that monitoring activities can be led and implemented by a variety of players not limited to aquaculture and IMTA managers, by engaging with and building synergy with researchers, local authorities, and community groups active in this field of work.

6.1 Monitoring considerations

At the start of any monitoring operation, it is important to establish a benchmark level of microplastic concentration and type at selected sites that can be visited regularly. The results of subsequent surveys can be compared with the benchmark levels to see whether there has been a change in concentration, perhaps as the result of policy interventions, or of a particular event (e.g., storm event or large-scale spill of litter or plastics). With systematic measurements over time, trends can be observed, informing on policy/regulatory needs as well as allowing assessment of the impacts on litter and microplastics from a specific source or event. Due to the inherent variability in the abundance of litter and

¹³ D5.4 Microplastics at IMTA labs and potential risks

microplastics in all aspects of the physical environment and within ecosystems, many replicates over several years of measurements may be required to detect a temporal trend with a sufficient statistical significance.

Figure 17. Question: What are the barriers to monitoring for emissions of microplastics in your region? (27 responses).

Stakeholder engagement indicated that there was a general lack of knowledge regarding regional policies and regional monitoring programmes (Figure 9) aimed at the emissions of microplastics, while the lack of policy, the high cost of monitoring, and the lack of technology all scored relatively equally high in terms of the potential barriers to monitoring for emissions of microplastics (Figure 17) - again indicating general uncertainty in this knowledge space.

Within ASTRAL a microplastic monitoring sensor (TA6) was developed as a standalone, benchtop, autonomously operating optical apparatus capable of systematically examining water samples under continuous flow (Figure 18). Its principal function is the precise identification of microscopically sized polymer particles, colloquially known as microplastics, while concurrently differentiating them from other naturally occurring particles within the scrutinized water sample. The imaging component features a commercial infinity-corrected microscope objective in conjunction with a tuneable lens, facilitating the acquisition of sharply focused images across the entire size spectrum of microplastics (ranging from 0.5 to 5mm). Complementing this arrangement is a high-speed industrial digital camera, ensuring expeditious image capture capabilities.

Figure 18. The final microplastic prototype MVP v2. showing [left] a 3D representation of the different elements composing the device, electronics highlighted in green, optics is red and water pump in blue; [right] image of the device.

6.2 Monitoring recommendations

Water sampling should be carried out using consistent methodologies as has been done during the ASTRAL project, and reporting should be standardised as proposed by international coordination bodies i.e., ICES, OSPAR, ++. Water sampling locations should be targeted to include litter and microplastics. It is recommended that inshore and coastal water for analysis can be extracted using pumps, targeting water 1-7 m below the surface and implementing sequential filtration using 1 mm, 300 μm and 10 μm mesh operated by light, compact and easy to use devices. The volume of collected water should aim at obtaining a sample representative of the general farm environment, with sufficient volumes (100 – 1000 liters per sample) to obtain a stable measurement. Replicates are recommended to facilitate coherent statistical treatment of the data obtained. Sampling during an occurrence of algal bloom in the area should be avoided where possible. Wherever relevant, sampling in rivers and estuarine ecosystems should be included for source monitoring to establish baseline levels of litter and understand the relationship to microplastics concentrations in nearby IMTAs facilities. The inherent variability – in the context of achieving statistical confidence - must be considered in the sampling strategy, regarding sampling frequencies. The variability in time scales of microplastics is an area of ongoing research, but in the absence of consolidated knowledge, annual monitoring is recommended.

It is recommended that monitoring programs consider a water and sediment sampling jointly, where possible. The rationale for this recommendation is that water and sediment sampling can often be carried out in the same sampling campaign and provide complementary, but not overlapping, information on the status and ultimately on the trends of plastic contamination. When water and

sediment sampling are performed together, a more complete picture of microplastics contamination of aquatic environments is provided, including potential exposure to organisms from the benthic to the pelagic. Furthermore, information from the aquatic and benthic environments provides contrasting temporal perspectives on plastic pollution. Sediments provide a more spatially and temporally integrated signal of plastic contamination, and while a variety of polymers can be found in sediment samples from beaches, sampling in the sublittoral zone will target particles with a higher sinking rate i.e. with densities greater than seawater (e.g., PVC). Water samples likely display more rapid fluctuations. However, capturing the relevant water mass can be challenging, thus hydrodynamic processes in the area need to be well characterised and understood to interpret the results. Oceanographic data such as seawater temperature, current strength and directionality, and the distribution of wind and wave frequencies and intensities should be collected for an integrated characterisation and understanding of the dynamics of microplastics pollution.

It is recommended that microplastics be monitored and reported according to their size, in categories. Analytical techniques such as vibrational spectroscopy-oriented methods yield information on number of particles (concentration), grain size, shape and mass. These outputs are useful beyond the baseline and trend monitoring of the IMTA farms, e.g. for research in environmental modelling towards refining particle distribution models. Small particle size classes ($< 10 \mu\text{m}$) can be useful in ecosystems research, e.g. regarding the uptake risk for aquatic life and the associated biological consequences. Furthermore, sediments layers near rivers and estuarine ecosystems can improve the understanding of historic and current levels of deposition.

The application of particle distribution models in aquatic environments is strongly recommended both at the preliminary stage of setting up a sampling and monitoring grid as well as periodically as the monitoring is ongoing, to refine model performance. A typical orthogonal transects sampling grid centred to the centre of the aquaculture production site with sampling sites at increasing distances from the centre is a recommended starting point where the reciprocal position of each transect is dictated by the output of the model.

Initially, identifying hot spots of MPs pollution, contributions from acute and diffuse sources, and the environmental behaviour of microplastics (i.e., sinking rates, interaction with biota) is important to characterise the environment under investigation. With an established and reliable data stream, with integrated environmental and microplastic sampling observations, projections for expected concentration and microplastic types can be tested, and predictions for the future can be made.

6.3 Recommendations for mitigation

Plastic pollution is a significant concern in aquaculture due to its potential negative impacts on aquatic ecosystems and marine life. The following mitigating actions should be considered:

- **Reduce Plastic Usage:** Minimize the use of plastic materials wherever possible. Biodegradable or reusable materials for containers, nets, ropes, and other equipment should be encouraged.
- **Proper Waste Management:** Proper waste management practices ensure that any plastic waste generated during aquaculture operations is collected and disposed of responsibly. Recycling and the prevention of plastic from entering waterways are important aspects of a waste management program.
- **Regular Cleanup:** Regular clean-up efforts in and around aquaculture facilities are required to remove any plastic debris that may have accumulated. This can help prevent plastics from entering water bodies and harming aquatic life.
- **Use of Eco-Friendly Alternatives:** Biodegradable fishing nets or compostable packaging materials with reduced environmental impact can help minimise plastic pollution in aquaculture.
- **Education and Awareness:** Aquaculture practitioners, employees, and stakeholders should be made aware of the potential impacts of plastic pollution on aquatic ecosystems and the importance of reducing plastic usage. Awareness campaigns and training programs should be promoted to encourage responsible practices.
- **Investment in Research and Innovation:** Research efforts to identify and develop innovative solutions for reducing plastic usage and pollution in aquaculture should be supported. This effort may involve developing new materials, technologies, or practices that are more sustainable and environmentally friendly.
- **Regulatory Measures:** Regulatory measures aimed at reducing plastic pollution in aquaculture should be complied with and advocated for. Policies and initiatives that promote the use of sustainable materials and practices within the industry should be developed and implemented.
- **Collaboration and Partnerships:** Collaboration with other stakeholders, including government agencies, environmental organizations, and industry associations, is an essential component of building capability to address plastic pollution in aquaculture collectively. Pooling resources and expertise can lead to more effective solutions.

By implementing these recommendations, aquaculture operations can help mitigate their contribution to plastic pollution and promote environmental sustainability in the industry.

7. Recommendations regarding technology

Engagement with aquaculture stakeholders across the Atlantic indicated a general lack of availability of affordable technology for monitoring the four parameters of interest discussed in this document, with the ability to monitor the emissions of microplastics ranking as the least accessible/affordable (Figure 17).

Figure 19. Question: In my region we have access to affordable technology to monitor for each of the following variables (29 responses). [1 = strongly disagree; 5 = strongly agree]

The ASTRAL project has successfully developed and implemented a range of innovative technologies to enhance monitoring and management in aquaculture systems. These comprise a set of innovative components or Technology Assets (TAs) that can be grouped according to the key goals of environmental monitoring and management (TA1, TA2, TA3), optimized biomass estimation and phytoplankton monitoring (TA4, TA5), addressing microplastic contamination (TA6), and data-driven decision-making (TA7); an overview of each of the TAs are provided in Table 2. One of the goals of the ASTRAL pool of technologies was to develop more affordable aquaculture technologies with limited investment – an aspect which is demonstrated in Table 2 with the estimated costs of the ASTRAL technologies versus the commercial benchmarks.

Table 2. Overview of the ASTRAL Technology Assets

Key goal	Technology asset (TA)	Final TRL	Estimated Cost	Commercial Benchmark**
Environmental Monitoring and Management	TA1 Biosensors	5	Vision-based: 1700 € MEMs-based: 700 €	
	TA2 Advanced water quality sensor	5		High-end spectrometer @12 000 €
	TA3 Low-cost IoT Kit	6	Basic Kit with minimal set of sensors starting at 4000 €.	
Optimized Biomass Estimation and Phytoplankton Monitoring	TA4 AI-vision sensor for biomass estimation	5	400 € to 500 €	
	TA5 AI-vision sensor for HAB monitoring	5	1300 €	FlowCAM @30 000 €
Addressing Microplastic Contamination	TA6 Microplastic monitoring sensor	5	V1: 5248,77€ V2: 7353,38 €	Microscope + software analysis @27 000 €
Data-driven Decision-making	TA7 AI Data Analytics platform	5		2000 €/year license

** Commercial Benchmark prices obtained between June and September 2023

General recommendations regarding the use of supportive technologies towards a more comprehensive environmental monitoring strategy include:

1. **Integration of Additional Parameters:** While biosensors and entry-level monitoring devices offer valuable data on oxygen levels, salinity and biomass, exploring the integration of additional parameters such as nutrient levels, pH, and other water quality indicators could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the aquaculture environment. This expansion would enable aquaculturists to make more informed decisions regarding feed management and overall ecosystem health.
2. **Enhanced AI Capabilities:** AI-driven algorithms can play a central role in data analysis and interpretation, and their success is dependent on continuous refinement and enhancement to improve the accuracy and efficiency of predictive models. Incorporating machine learning techniques to adapt to dynamic environmental conditions and refining the AI interfaces for user-friendly experiences could further empower aquaculture practitioners.

3. **Scalability and Accessibility:** Ensuring that the developed solutions can be easily scaled to accommodate various aquaculture operations, regardless of size or location, will broaden their applicability and impact. This involves addressing potential cost barriers, optimizing energy consumption, and simplifying installation and maintenance processes.
4. **Cross-Technology Integration:** Exploring opportunities for cross-technology integration could enhance synergies between different components of an IMTA system. For instance, integrating data from a microplastic sensor with phytoplankton monitoring could provide a more holistic view of environmental health. Such integrations could lead to a more interconnected and insightful monitoring network.
5. **Cybersecurity Measures:** Given the increasing reliance on digital platforms and cloud-based systems, implementing robust cybersecurity measures is crucial to safeguard sensitive aquaculture data. Enhancing security protocols within online and cloud-based platforms will ensure the integrity and confidentiality of the information being collected and analyzed.
6. **Stakeholder Collaboration:** Fostering collaboration with key stakeholders, including aquaculturists, research institutions and environmental agencies, can provide valuable insights and facilitate the customization of technologies based on specific regional needs. This collaborative approach ensures that the technologies align with industry requirements, contribute meaningfully to sustainable aquaculture practices and support the ongoing development of improved policies.
7. **Continued Research and Innovation:** The aquaculture industry is dynamic, and ongoing research and innovation are vital to staying ahead of emerging challenges. Encouraging participation in continued research initiatives, exploring emerging technologies, and staying abreast of advancements in related fields will position IMTA farming as a catalyst for ongoing improvement and innovation within the aquaculture sector.

8. Summary and Conclusion

This document provides an overview of the regional and system-specific vulnerabilities and considerations regarding climate change, HABs, pathogens and emissions of microplastics in the context of aquaculture and IMTA across the Atlantic. Overall, there is a comparatively lower awareness of the policies, techniques, and available technology for monitoring the emissions of microplastics in relation to the other three factors - thus the recommendations coming out of ASTRAL will be extremely valuable and important to drive this research space beyond the state of the art. The report shows some of the aquaculture stakeholder perceptions regarding the barriers to monitoring for relevant parameters, and has demonstrated where ASTRAL have addressed these issues through the development of innovative technologies in support of routine monitoring. The indicators/parameters, risk factors, as well as the general and specific recommendations for monitoring of climate change variables, HABs, and pathogens have been summarised per system type for Open-ocean systems (Table 3), Land-based partial recirculation systems (Table 4), and Land-based recirculation systems (Table 5) below. The general and specific monitoring recommendations, including recommendations for mitigation, for microplastic emissions is provided in Table 6.

Table 3. Open ocean systems monitoring recommendations per risk type.

Indicators	Risk factors	General monitoring recommendations	Specific monitoring recommendations
Climate Change			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sea surface temperature (SST) Sea surface salinity (SSS) pH Partial pressure of Carbon Dioxide (pCO₂) Dissolved Oxygen (O₂) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General sparsity of Nitrate data System is completely open to the ambient environment and most vulnerable to climate change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate variable monitoring should preferably take place at the same location(s) and same time of day over long periods Aquaculture operations should store and quality control their own data, to assess environmental changes towards safeguarding their business Aquaculture operations should be encouraged to share their environmental monitoring data for research purposes Regionally optimized satellite data products (e.g. SST) are useful for assessing long term trends 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature monitored twice daily at the surface and another sample depth to assess stratification Dissolved oxygen daily at facility and another position upstream/downstream Total Nitrogen measured regularly (weekly to monthly)
Harmful Algal Blooms			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Various dinoflagellates and some diatom species Different species bloom at different times between spring and late summer Different species have different nutrient, temperature and turbulence preferences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> System completely open to the ambient environment Monitoring of remote locations can be difficult 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chlorophyll a (fluorescence) for non-species specific algal biomass estimates: in situ (continuous), field samples (daily) or satellite data (daily) Species identification via microscopy or technology solution, e.g. flow-cam, planktoscope: weekly, or adjusted according to season/risk Nutrients and ratios, e.g. Nitrate, Phosphate, Ammonium, Silica, dissolved organic matter: field samples (monthly) Salinity: in situ or field samples (weekly) Currents: satellite data or models (daily), in situ (continuous) Temperature and upwelling: satellite data or models (daily), field sampling (daily), or in situ (continuous) Stratification: In situ temperature and salinity at surface and appropriate depth (daily/continuous) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decreased monitoring frequency in winter or when site not active Assess river run-off, precipitation, tidal cycles as required Make use of regional HAB bulletins/predictions when possible
Pathogens			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bacteria: <i>Aeromonas salmonicida</i>, <i>Tenacibaculum spp.</i>, <i>Vibrio spp.</i>, <i>Moritella viscosa</i> Virus: <i>Novirhabdovirus</i>; <i>Salmoid alphavirus</i> (SAV); Oyster Herpes Virus (OsHV) Other: Sea lice, Protist, Oomycetes, fungi 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> System is completely open to the ambient environment high susceptibility to several bacteria, viruses and parasites more prevalent in spring/summer when water temperatures increase Outbreaks more prone during overcrowding and increased stress 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wireless sensor network for continuous monitoring of water quality parameters; specifically temperature increase and Oxygen decrease Monitoring animal behaviour as early warning sign Have specific sampling protocols in place for each type of analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lateral flow biosensors for rapid detection of viruses Biosensors in tagged fish to provide real-time data on fish stress/health Light-emitting diode biosensors to reduce the sea lice infestation

Table 4. Land-based partial recirculation systems monitoring recommendations per risk type.

Indicators	Risk factors	General monitoring recommendations	Specific monitoring recommendations
Climate Change			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sea surface temperature (SST) Sea surface salinity (SSS) pH Partial pressure of Carbon Dioxide (pCO₂) Dissolved Oxygen (O₂) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General sparsity of Nitrate data System is only partially open to the ambient environment through intake water pumped into system Not as vulnerable to climate change as the open systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate variable monitoring should preferably take place at the same location(s) and same time of day over long periods Aquaculture operations should store and quality control their own data, to assess environmental changes towards safeguarding their business Aquaculture operations should be encouraged to share their environmental monitoring data for research purposes Regionally optimized satellite data products (e.g. SST) are useful for assessing long term trends 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature monitored twice daily at the surface and another sample depth to assess stratification Dissolved oxygen daily at facility and another position upstream/downstream Total Nitrogen measured regularly (weekly to monthly)
Harmful Algal Blooms			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Various dinoflagellates and some diatom species Different species bloom at different times between spring and late summer Different species have different nutrient, temperature and turbulence preferences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Generally lower risk associated with HABs due to ability of system to go onto full recirculation for 12-48 hours in cases of severe blooms. Risks vary between cultured species and different HAB species Increased occurrence of HABs from spring to late summer General HAB risks include: clogging of gills, production of toxins - affecting animal health and consumption safety, decreased dissolved oxygen following high biomass bloom collapse 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chlorophyll a (fluorescence) for non-species specific algal biomass estimates: in situ (continuous), field samples (daily) or satellite data (daily) Species identification via microscopy or technology solution, e.g. flow-cam, planktoscope: weekly, or adjusted according to season/risk Nutrients and ratios, e.g. Nitrate, Phosphate, Ammonium, Silica, dissolved organic matter: field samples (monthly) Salinity: in situ or field samples (weekly) Currents: satellite data or models (daily), in situ (continuous) Temperature and upwelling: satellite data or models (daily), field sampling (daily), or in situ (continuous) Stratification: In situ temperature and salinity at surface and appropriate depth (daily/continuous) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decreased enumeration frequency in winter Increase enumeration frequency (sub-daily) when bloom is detected at water intake location Make use of remote sensing products of Chlorophyll a and phytoplankton type whenever possible to assess potential bloom location and movement relative to intake pipe location Monitor tides (i.e. during bloom prioritize pumping water into system at high tide)
Pathogens			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bacteria: <i>Vibrio</i> spp., Rickettsial like – organisms, Cyanobacteria, <i>Streptococcus</i> Virus: <i>Haliotid herpesvirus 1</i> (HahV-1) Other: <i>Protozoa</i>, <i>Polychaetes</i>, <i>Oomycetes</i>, <i>Sabellid</i>, <i>Amoeba</i> - <i>Paramoeba invadiens</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> low incidence of disease outbreaks Temperature rise Outbreaks more prone during overcrowding and increased stress 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wireless sensor network for continuous monitoring of water quality parameters; specifically temperature increase and Oxygen decrease Monitoring animal behaviour as early warning sign Have specific sampling protocols in place for each type of analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> analysis of eDNA samples collected from the system to monitor the presence or change in abundance (increase) of potential pathogens qPCR for virulence related genes of <i>Vibrio</i> species lateral flow biosensors for herpesvirus multi-locus barcoding for the identification of different parasite

Table 5. Land-based recirculation systems monitoring recommendations per risk type.

Indicators	Risk factors	General monitoring recommendations	Specific monitoring recommendations
Climate Change			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sea surface temperature (SST) Sea surface salinity (SSS) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General sparsity of Nitrate data System is only partially open to the ambient environment through intake water pumped into system Not as vulnerable to climate change as the open systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate variable monitoring should preferably take place at the same location(s) and same time of day over long periods Aquaculture operations should store and quality control their own data, to assess environmental changes towards safeguarding their business Aquaculture operations should be encouraged to share their environmental monitoring data for research purposes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature and salinity of water monitored at intake on a daily basis
Harmful Algal Blooms			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Various dinoflagellates and some diatom species Cyanobacteria bloom in estuaries and lagoons Different species bloom at different times Risks vary between cultured species and different HAB species Different species have different nutrient, temperature and turbulence preferences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Very low risk to IMTA due to recirculation of water in cultivation system Risks vary between cultured species and different HAB species General HAB risks include: clogging of gills, production of toxins - affecting animal health and consumption safety, decreased dissolved oxygen following high biomass bloom collapse 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chlorophyll a (fluorescence) for non-species specific algal biomass estimates: in situ (continuous), field samples (daily) or satellite data (daily) Species identification via microscopy or technology solution, e.g. flow-cam, planktoscope: weekly, or adjusted according to season/risk Nutrients and ratios, e.g. Nitrate, Phosphate, Ammonium, Silica, dissolved organic matter: field samples (monthly) Salinity: in situ or field samples (weekly) Currents: satellite data or models (daily), in situ (continuous) Temperature and upwelling: satellite data or models (daily), field sampling (daily), or in situ (continuous) Stratification: In situ temperature and salinity at surface and appropriate depth (daily/continuous) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water pumped from estuary is treated before use in cultivation systems
Pathogens			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bacteria: <i>Vibrio spp.</i>, Rickettsial like – organisms, Cyanobacteria, <i>Streptococcus</i> Virus: <i>Haliotid herpesvirus 1</i> (HahV-1) Other: <i>Protozoa</i>, <i>Polychaetes</i>, <i>Oomycetes</i>, <i>Sabellid</i>, <i>Amoeba</i> - <i>Paramoeba invadiens</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> low incidence of disease outbreaks Rainy season, low salinity High temperature and luminosity Outbreaks more prone during overcrowding and increased stress 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wireless sensor network for continuous monitoring of water quality parameters; specifically temperature increase and Oxygen decrease Monitoring animal behaviour as early warning sign Have specific sampling protocols in place for each type of analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> analysis of eDNA samples collected from the biofloc to monitor the presence or change in abundance (increase) of potential pathogens biosensors (LFB and wireless sensor) digital qPCR

Table 6. Monitoring recommendations for Microplastics.

General monitoring recommendations	Specific monitoring recommendations	Mitigation recommendations
Microplastics		
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Establish a benchmark at a regularly visited site• Use consistent methodologies• Standardize reporting as proposed by international coordinating bodies• Sampling in rivers and estuarine ecosystems should be included for source monitoring to establish baseline levels of litter• Oceanographic info (SST, current strength & direction, wind and wave strength & direction) can support an integrated characterization of the dynamics of MP pollution• Application of particle distribution models in aquatic environments is strongly recommended	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Sampling locations should be targeted to include litter and microplastics• Water extracted using pumps, 1-7m below surface• Sequential filtration using 1 mm, 300 µm and 10 µm mesh• Filter sufficient volumes (100 – 1000 liters per sample) to obtain a stable measurement• Avoid sampling during an algal bloom• In the absence of concrete knowledge of sampling interval required, annual monitoring is recommended• Monitor and report MPs according to size and category; number of particles (concentration), grain size, shape and mass also useful• Do joint water and sediment sampling if possible	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Reduce plastic usage• Proper waste management• Regular cleanup• Use of eco-friendly alternatives• Education and awareness• Investment in research and innovation• Regulatory measures• Collaboration and partnerships

Appendix A

ONLINE WORKSHOP

Monday 19th June 2023, 14:00– 15:30 CEST
Registration link: <https://shorturl.at/gpBGR>

Community input: Recommendations for monitoring the effects of climate change and emerging pollutants in the Atlantic aquaculture sector

This workshop will provide a brief overview of the All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture (ASTRAL) project and showcase some of the project's provisional results relating to regional investigations into the environmental threats of climate change and emerging pollutants such as pathogens, microplastics and harmful algal blooms (HABs) in the context of aquaculture. The workshop is open to aquaculturalists and interested or affected parties across the Atlantic, and aims to provide an interactive platform for feedback and discussion on these topics.

- 14:00– Welcome and workshop format
- Marie Smith (CSIR)
- 14:05– The ASTRAL project
- Elisa Ravagnan (NORCE)
- 14:15– Climate vulnerability along the Atlantic coast
- Nadine Goris (NORCE)
- 14:25– Conditions favouring Harmful Algal Bloom development
- Francisca Vermeulen (SAMS)
- 14:35– Pathogens: Past, Present and Future
- Marina Martín Sandoval (Leitat)
- 14:45– Microplastics in aquaculture systems: Past, Present and Future
- Alessio Gomiero (NORCE)
- 14:55– Q&A, Community interaction

This workshop is organised by CSIR with the support of ASTRAL partners.

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Figure A1. The flyer and agenda for the aquaculture stakeholder workshop held in June 2023.